

IN-FET
Ionic modulation for Epilepsy Treatment

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1. Executive summary

This report provides a structured overview of the dissemination actions undertaken by the IN-FET project partners during the first year of activity to ensure an appropriate degree of visibility of the project to all stakeholder categories, from the scientific community to the general public. Despite COVID-19 related restrictions, numerous events and actions were undertaken and publications were prepared or submitted, as documented below. A brief outlook on the next year planned or expected actions is given in the last section and in the summary table. A copy of this public document is also available on www.zenodo.org.

2. Dissemination actions

For the first year of the IN-FET project, dissemination activities were primarily addressed to the general public, rather than to a scientific audience. Given the delays enforced by the closing of the laboratories, dissemination efforts have been focused mostly toward the student's community (also as an aid toward the recruiting campaign in support of the project) and to the general public (also by means of the website and the social media). Participation to hybrid or remote events allowed the project partners to spread the voice about the project. Engagement at the local or national level was also pursued, mainly via press releases, articles on the press or weekly magazines, etc.

2.1 Dissemination through websites and social media

The **IN-FET website**, www.in-fet.eu, was launched in February 2020, as the first deliverable of the Management, RRI, Dissemination, Networking, Exploitation Work Package (WP5). Throughout the year, we regularly updated the sections "Events" and "Press and Dissemination" of the website, to announce the events involving the IN-FET project consortium, or to publish press release and divulgation articles that focused on the IN-FET project.

We also regularly posted on the IN-FET Twitter (54 followers) and Facebook (36 people liked the page) profiles to advertise our public talks or to engage with the public, discuss neuroprosthetics and give more visibility to the IN-FET project and consortium.

We opened a **YouTube channel** for the project (8 people subscribed to it, to date), where we uploaded the videos of our public outreach events: <https://www.youtube.com/channel/UC4299VceGDOSVqmFTgHTIEw> (58 visualizations in total).

The description of the IN-FET project has also been published on our **consortium partner MCS' website**: <https://www.multichannelsystems.com/research-projects/fet>, on the website of the Neuronal Dynamics Laboratory at SISSA <https://www.giugliano.info/lab/doku.php> and on the Twitter, Facebook and LinkedIn profiles of several consortium members.

2.2 Dissemination through the press

After the kickoff meeting, in February 2020, a **press release**, written with the help of the press office in SISSA, was published on the website of SISSA, on the IN FET website and in the project's social accounts Twitter and Facebook. The press release briefly described the project, making its purpose accessible to all types of audience.

<https://www.in-fet.eu/node/12>

<http://phdneurobiology.sissa.it/eng/news/in-fet.aspx>

<https://www.sissa.it/news/eu-funds-%E2%82%AC3m-project-develop-nanodevices-against-epilepsy-and-parkinson%E2%80%99s>

A science **divulgation article** was published in June 2020 in Panorama, an Italian magazine. The title of the article was "Questioni di testa". In the article, Prof. Dr. Michele Giugliano explained how stimulating the brain with natural ionic currents (the basic principle behind the IN-FET project) may represent a new treatment for Parkinson.

<https://www.in-fet.eu/node/13>

An **article** about the IN-FET project was published in July 2020 in the monthly magazine of the University of Modena and Reggio Emilia. The title of the article was: "Oltre i confini: quattro progetti tra nanoelettronica, nanotecnologie e neuroscienze" and it described the aim of 4 Horizon 2020 funded projects, in the area of nanotechnologies and neurosciences.

<https://www.in-fet.eu/node/15>

2.3 Dissemination through scientific papers

2.3.1 Under revision or preprints

1. *Spike–frequency adaptation is modulated by interacting currents in an Hodgkin-Huxley-type model: Role of the Na,K–ATPase.* **Renaud B. Jolivet**, Pierre J. Magistretti, 2020. Preprint: <https://doi.org/10.1101/2020.06.12.148437>; Altmetric score 7 (top 25%).
2. *On the role of theory and modeling in neuroscience.* Daniel Levenstein, Veronica A.Alvarez, Asohan Amarasingham, Habiba Azab, Richard C. Gerkin, Andrea Hasenstaub, Ramakrishnan Iyer, Renaud B. Jolivet, Sarah Marzen, Joseph D. Monaco , Astrid A. Prinz, Salma Quraishi, Fidel Santamaria, Sabyasachi Shivkumar, Matthew F. Singh, David B. Stockton, Roger Traub, Horacio G. Rotstein, Farzan Nadim, A. David Redish: Arxiv, 2020. Preprint: <http://arxiv.org/abs/2003.13825>; Altmetric score 63 (top 5%).
3. *Modelling of vertical nano-needles as sensing devices for neuronal signal recordings.* Federico Leva, Pierpaolo Palestri, Luca Selmi (2020). TechRxiv. Preprint. <https://doi.org/10.36227/techrxiv.12585086.v1>.
4. *Comparative performance of mutual information and transfer entropy for analyzing the balance of information flow and energy consumption at synapses.* Mireille Conrad and **Renaud B. Jolivet**, 2020. Preprint: <https://doi.org/10.1101/2020.06.01.127399>.

2.3.2 Published

1. *Plasticity and Adaptation in Neuromorphic Biohybrid Systems.* Richard George, Michela Chiappalone, Michele Giugliano, Timothée Levi, Stefano Vassanelli, Johannes Partzsch, Christian Mayr. iScience. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.isci.2020.101589>
2. *General model and equivalent circuit for the chemical noise spectrum associated to surface charge fluctuation in potentiometric sensors.* L. J. Mele, P. Palestri and L. Selmi. IEEE Sensors Journal. <https://doi.org/10.1109/JSEN.2020.3038036>.
3. *Modelling Neuromodulated Information Flow and Energetic Consumption at Thalamic Relay Synapses.* Mireille Conrad and **Renaud B. Jolivet**. Lect. Notes Comput. Sci. 12397: 649-658 (2020). http://dx.doi.org/10.1007/978-3-030-61616-8_52.

2.4 Dissemination through other means

1. In February and March 2020, the IN-FET project coordinator, Prof. Dr. Michele Giugliano volunteered for two events (one lecture and one debate/interview) organised by SISSA for schools: a series of appointments where students from primary, middle and high school met the scientists working in SISSA and learned about the research they carry out, resulting often in enthusiastic reactions from both sides, the students and the professors.

<https://www.youtube.com/watch?v=Mjz4VCeKKsM>

2. In September 2020, in the frame of ESOF 2020 and Science in the City Festival, our IN-FET project coordinator Prof. Dr. Michele Giugliano, together with Prof. Dr. Pierpaolo Palestri and Prof. Dr. Luca Selmi, members of the IN-FET consortium, held a public lecture on "Nanotechnologies and nanoelectronics to cure the brain". Chairman of the talk was Dr. Valentina Perrera, IN-FET project manager. The public lecture took place inside the seminar room of the Revoltella Museum, downtown in Trieste and was streamed live on YouTube

<https://www.youtube.com/watch?v=sHMQstkcw-o>

About 40 people were in the audience in Museo Revoltella and other 70 people followed the event live in the Science in the City Festival YouTube channel. The video available on the Science in the City Festival YouTube channel has now reached 309 views (updated to 14 December 2020). The video of the lecture is also permanently visible on the IN-FET YouTube channel, where it reached 28 views (updated to 14 December 2020).

<https://www.youtube.com/watch?v=sHSjptNfq8&t=702s>

<https://www.youtube.com/watch?v=sHMQstkcw-o>

<https://events.scienceinthecity2020.eu/en/nanotechnologies-and-nanoelectronics-to-cure-the-brain>

3. We produced and distributed a leaflet to all consortium members and published on our website and social accounts, to synthetically describe the goal of the IN-FET project and the diversity of its consortium composition.

4. Prof. Dr. Michele Giugliano, together with Dr. Renaud Jolivet, participated as speakers to the [MCAA Virtual Conference on Research and Democracy](#) on the 6 Nov 2020 15:45 - 16:45 CET, with the talk: At the interface of AI, Neuroscience and Policy.

A brief summary of the workshop can be found here:

<https://medium.com/marie-curie-alumni/live-from-the-mcaa-virtual-conference-5e5a3114772c>.

About 50 viewers listened to the live broadcast. Additionally, the recorded workshop is available on YouTube here <https://youtu.be/GMQQUvalGJA> and here <https://youtu.be/kvPMzET9cOU>, and had accumulated approximately 60 views by Dec. 2020. The workshop was heavily advertised on Twitter by multiple accounts before and after the event.

2.5 Planned dissemination events

- On 03-04 February 2021, Dr. Jannis Meents, Head of Research Projects at IN-FET consortium member MCS, will participate as speaker at the [2nd Workshop on Next Gen Organ-on-Chip & Organoids](https://www.csem.ch/page.aspx?pid=155967) (<https://www.csem.ch/page.aspx?pid=155967>), which is organized by the Centre Suisse d'Electronique et de Microtechnique (CSEM) in Switzerland. The talk will be entitled: "Next Generation Micro Electrode Array Devices".
- Talks are on-going with partners of the HERMES (www.hermes-fet.eu) and BEFERROSYNAPTIC (www.beferrosynaptic.eu) H2020 projects to organize two joint workshops later in 2021 with invited and contributed talks.

3. Summary table

Means of communication	Main target groups	Purpose	Actions done	Date	
IN-FET Twitter profile, IN-FET Facebook profile	ALL	To engage with the public, discuss about neuroprosthetics and give more visibility to the IN-FET project	Opening the profiles and posting periodically	February 2020	Twitter 54 followers; Facebook 36 likes, as of 14.12.2020
Project website	ALL	To create a web presence for the project and make the community aware of the IN-FET project's main aim and consortium composition	The website has been created and advertised on the social channels of IN-FET	February 2020	
YouTube channel	ALL	To upload the videos of our public outreach and scientific dissemination events	Opening the channel, uploading the videos, advertising the channel on the twitter and facebook accounts and on the IN-FET website	February 2020	8 subscribers as of 14.12.2020
Kickoff meeting press release	ALL	To communicate that the IN-FET project was launched and briefly describe its purpose	The press release was published on the website of SISSA, on the IN FET website and in the project's social accounts Twitter and Facebook	February 2020	
SISSA 4 Schools	high school students	To allow students from school to get in touch with scientists and familiarise with their research activities	A series of appointments where students from primary, middle and high school met the scientists working in SISSA and learned about the research they carry out	February - March 2020	
Science divulgation article by Panorama	ALL	To inform the public on the state-of-the-art technologies in neuroscience	Michele Giugliano explained how stimulating the brain with natural ionic currents (the basic principle behind the IN-FET project) may represent a new treatment for Parkinson	June 2020	
Article about the IN-FET project published in the monthly magazine of the University of Modena and Reggio Emilia	ALL, students, professors and staff, mainly from University of Modena and Reggio Emilia	To announce the involvement of UNIMORE in Horizon 2020 funded projects and describe these project's main aim	The article described the scientific focus of 4 different Horizon 2020 funded projects involving nanotechnologies, nano electronics and neuroscience	July 2020	

Public talk 'Nanotechnologies and nanoelectronics to cure the brain'	ALL	To take part in the ESO2020 conference with a public outreach event centered on IN-FET project	The public lecture took place inside the seminar room of the Revoltella Museum, downtown in Trieste and was streamed live on YouTube	September 2020	
Leaflet	ALL	To have a brochure for a quick presentation of IN-FET project's main aim and consortium composition	The leaflet highlights the most important aspects of the IN-FET project and summarises its goal. It has been distributed to all consortium members	November 2020	
Scientific publications or preprints in peer reviewed journals	Neuroscientists/scientists	Scientific dissemination of novel findings and results obtained within the IN-FET project	<p><i>Plasticity and Adaptation in Neuromorphic Biohybrid Systems</i>, George, Richard et al. iScience, Volume 23, Issue 10, 101589</p> <p><i>General model and equivalent circuit for the chemical noise spectrum associated to surface charge fluctuation in potentiometric sensors</i>. L. J. Mele, P. Palestri and L. Selmi. IEEE Sensors Journal. https://doi.org/10.1109/JSEN.2020.3038036</p> <p><i>Spike-frequency adaptation is modulated by interacting currents in an Hodgkin-Huxley-type model: Role of the Na,K-ATPase</i>. Renaud Blaise Jolivet, Pierre J. Magistretti. bioRxiv 2020.06.12.148437; doi:https://doi.org/10.1101/2020.06.12.148437</p> <p><i>Modelling of vertical nano-needles as sensing devices for neuronal signal recordings</i>. Federico Leva, Pierpaolo Palestri, Luca Selmi (2020). TechRxiv. Preprint. https://doi.org/10.36227/techrxiv.12585086.v1</p> <p><i>On the role of theory and modeling in neuroscience</i>. Daniel Levenstein, et al. Arxiv. Preprint. http://arxiv.org/abs/2003.13825</p> <p><i>Modelling Neuromodulated Information Flow and Energetic Consumption at Thalamic Relay Synapses</i>. Mireille Conrad and Renaud B. Jolivet. Lect. Notes Comput. Sci. 12397: 649-658 (2020). http://dx.doi.org/10.1007/978-3-030-61616-8_52.</p>	October 2020	
Online workshop	Neuroscientists/scientists	MCAA virtual conference on Research and democracy. A talk to discuss the interface between Neuroscience, AI and policy	https://marie-curie.meetingbox.io/app/research-and-democracy/?show=events&viewPage=919 Fri 6 Nov at 15.45 CET	November 2020	Reach as of Dec. 2020, about 110 viewers total.

Table1. Summary of the dissemination activities per target community and action.

4. Conclusions and outlook

The first year of the project led to a more than adequate total number of dissemination actions, especially toward the general public, understandably so in view of the delays and difficulties related to the COVID-19 pandemic. Links to other projects in the same or similar research areas have been established which are expected to enhance the effectiveness of the outcomes and expand the perimeter of stakeholders reached. As project activities are beginning to produce results of scientific relevance, IN-FET partners will steer their main dissemination actions toward scientific papers on peer reviewed journals and conferences.